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SHORT NOTES / BREVI NOTE

DESIRÉE FALZON, BENJAMIN METZGER & VICTOR FALZON

FIRST RECORD OF *BRACHYCARPUS BIUNGUICULATUS* (LUCAS, 1846) (*Decapoda Palaemonidae*) IN THE MALTESE ISLANDS

Nuova segnalazione di Brachycarpus biunguiculatus (Lucas, 1846) (*Decapoda Palaemonidae*) per le isole Maltesi

The Twoclaw Shrimp *Brachycarpus biunguiculatus* (Lucas, 1846) is a marine decapod that inhabits shallow to deep waters (10–190m) (WoRMS, 2024). The genus has a cosmopolitan distribution, with *B. biunguiculatus* being the only species of this genus so far recorded in the Mediterranean Basin (D'UDEKEM D'AKOZ, 1999, KAMPOURIS & EXADACTYLOS, 2023). Recent records of *B. biunguiculatus* in the Mediterranean are from Libya (RIZGALLA, 2021) and from islands in the south Aegean Sea, namely Santorini (KAMPOURIS *et al.*, 2018), Rhodes (KONDYLATOS *et al.*, 2020) and Nisyros (BATJAKAS & KAMPOURIS, 2020). A recent record, also from Hellenic waters, documents testimonies by divers encountering the shrimp during nocturnal excursions from Sifnos (Cyclades Islands) (KAMPOURIS & EXADACTYLOS, 2023). Apart from the recent record from Libya, observations from the Central Mediterranean Sea have so far been restricted to Italian waters (SPINELLI *et al.*, 2017). This short note describes the first documented record of *B. biunguiculatus* in the Maltese Islands.

Three snorkelling sessions were held in an area on the northeast coast of mainland Malta, covering the first evening hours after dark (21.00–23.00 hrs), on July 27, and August 3 and 17, 2024. Within the area halfway inside Xemxija Bay (Fig. 1), two sites were covered: a stretch on the south-east-facing side of the bay, and a stretch on the north-west-facing side of nearby Daħlet il-Fekruna, a small, sheltered inlet within Xemxija Bay.

Three observers, including two of the authors were slowly moving at the sea surface along the rocky shoreline, scanning the surface of the submerged cliff face, including small caves and crevices by means of dive torches. Photographs were taken in situ underwater, using submersible digital cameras Olympus TG-5 and OM Systems TG-7 and dive torches. At no point was any specimen caught or handled. Specimens of *B. biunguiculatus* were recorded on both dates and at both sites of the area. The number of specimens observed in each session varied between six and ten. The shrimp was found in the upper infralittoral zone at a depth of just 0.15–0.5 metres, inhabiting crevices and holes on the rockface. The shrimps' reflecting eyes made the specimens immediately evident in the torch beam. However, all specimens exhibited strong negative phototaxis, quickly hiding away from the light in small caves and crevices. Therefore, taking sufficiently clear photographs for identification required waiting for the animals to re-emerge from hiding, usually after 10 to 30 seconds. In gener-

Fig. 1 — Map of area of observations (Drawing by V. Falzon).

al, the shrimps were encountered solitarily moving around on the rock and between the epiphytal and epizootic community, presumably foraging. During locomotion, forward and backward movements, including the caridoid escape reaction (lobstering), could be observed. Additional to the photo documentation, video footage was taken of some of the specimens. Figures 2–5 show three different specimens. Identification in situ was challenging due to the specimens' fast retreat into recesses in the rockface on being disturbed by torchlight and was only possible from subsequent examination of photographic material. The species' identification was confirmed consulting DORIS (2022), an online forum of the French diving federation FFESSM and its biology commission CNEBS.

The habitat where the specimens were observed stretches along the vertical rock face on two sides of a small coralline limestone promontory that plunges into the sea down to a depth ranging from 3–10 metres. The southeast-facing side receives long hours of sunshine, while the northeast-facing side receives little direct sunlight, the deeper areas being in permanent shade for most of the year.

The rockface is characterised by a multitude of small crevices, many of which are completely covered by algal growth, providing suitable hiding places. Marine vegetation in the immediate area where the species was observed was composed of several algae, including *Jania rubens*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, and encrusting red algae, including *Peyssonnelia* sp. Also present in the area were several cnidarians (e.g. *Eudendrium* sp., *Astroides calycularis*), sponges (e.g. *Chondrilla nucula*, *Ircinia* sp., *Spirastrella cunctatrix*), tunicates (e.g. *Cystodytes dellachiajei*, *Botrylloides leachii*), and the encrusting bryozoan *Reptadeonella violacea*. Other crustaceans observed in the area during the sessions included *Eryphia verrucosa*, *Pagurus anachoretus*, and two other shrimp species, namely *Gnathopylulum elegans* and *Palaemon serratus*. Two specimens of the brittlestar *Ophioderma longicauda* were noted in the vicinity during the second session. Fish inhabiting the crevices, observed by day included *Apogon imberbis*, *Lipophrys trigloides*, *Parablennius incognitus*, *P. gattorugine*, *P. zvonimiri*, *Tripterygion melanurum*, and *T. tripteronotum*.

Figs. 2-5 — 2. Low quality photograph, possibly showing female carrying eggs (photo by B. Metzger); 3. Specimen showing dorsal stripes and light-tipped claws (photo by B. Metzger); 4. Photograph with lateral dark blue blotches on abdominal segments (photo by D. Falzon); 5. Photograph showing more uniform dorsal color and lateral blue blotches (photo by B. Metzger).

The presence of several specimens of the species in two subsites of a small area during just three visits in combination with high availability of similar habitat along large stretches of Maltese coast, makes *B. biunguiculatus* likely a common and widespread inhabitant of the rocky upper infralittoral in Malta. The fact that this medium sized and colourful shrimp had not been recorded from the Maltese Islands before could be due to the species' nocturnal and reclusive habits. Indeed, the overall sparsity of records of *B. biunguiculatus* across the Mediterranean and in general has been attributed to these habits before (KAMPOURIS & EXADACTYLOS, 2023). The species' nocturnal activity has been confirmed in previous studies (KIRINCIC, 2003; WIRTZ, 1995). However, the strongly negative phototactic reactions observed make more precise assessments of abundance and distribution challenging and prevent from the recording of natural behaviour (such as foraging, mating, etc.) which is not disrupted by the beam of the dive torch. Contrasting with data from literature (WoRMS), stating the species' depth range at 10–190m, in Malta *B. biunguiculatus* was observed in the upper infralittoral. To the present authors it remains currently unclear whether the species indeed inhabits this zone permanently or can be found there only temporarily due to vertical movements. Such vertical movements have been described in many marine organisms and could follow a diurnal periodicity; alternatively, they could be linked to certain stages of the species' life cycle, such as mating, breeding, etc. (BANDARA *et al.*, 2021; BOS *et al.*, 2021; PINTI *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, it is as yet unclear whether the two different colourations noted in the specimen photos represent a distinctive sexual feature or whether the blue blotches seen on the ovigerous female are dependent on reproductive status.

More surveys would be required to assess the wider distribution, further habitat preferences, abundance, reproductive behaviour, and status of this photogenic but secretive palaemonid shrimp in Maltese waters more thoroughly.

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Authors' addresses – D. FALZON, 34, Triq is-Sieqja, H'Attard ATD 1712 (Malta), email: vdfalzon@gmail.com; B. METZGER, 26/1 Triq L-Immakulata Kuncizzjoni, Gżira, GZR 1141, email: blm-researcher@gmail.com; V. FALZON, Triq is-Sieqja, H'Attard ATD 1712 (Malta), email: vdfalzon@gmail.com